

SYNtzuLu: A Tiny RISC-V-Controlled SNN Processor for Real-Time Sensor Data Analysis on Low-Power FPGAs

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Abstract—Spiking Neural Networks (SNNs) are energy- and performance-efficient tools that have been found to be very useful in AI applications at the edge. This paper introduces SYNtzuLu, an SNN processing element designed to be used in low-cost and low-power FPGA devices for near-sensor data analysis. The system is equipped with a RISC-V subsystem responsible for controlling the input/output and setting runtime parameters, thus increasing its flexibility. We evaluated the system, which was implemented on a Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA, in various use cases employing SNNs with accuracy comparable to the state-of-the-art. SYNtzuLu dissipates a maximum power of 12.05 mW when performing SNN inference, which can be reduced to an average of just 1.45 mW through the use of dynamic power management.

Index Terms—Spiking neural network (SNN), edge AI, field programmable gate array (FPGA), energy efficiency, RISC-V.

I. INTRODUCTION

SPIKING Neural Networks (SNNs) are becoming an increasingly widespread tool for enhancing the energy efficiency of near-sensor execution of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tasks. These networks operate on event-based data, significantly reducing computational workload and power consumption. Neuromorphic processors efficiently exploit event sparsity, however, they cannot still be considered mainstream in the market due to costs and availability. An attractive alternative technology target to execute SNNs is provided by FPGA devices. They offer flexible memory, DSP capabilities, and reconfigurable logic, useful to map use-case-specific blocks for spike encoding and decoding, i.e. converting the input-output of the task into spikes and vice versa [1].

The literature describes FPGA-based SNN processors using two schemes: clock-driven, where computations, as neurons

integration and synapses evaluation, occur at each time step, and event-driven, where computations are more sparse, as triggered only by spike events, but more complex. Moreover, three alternatives exist when it comes to encoding strategies: frame-based rate encoding, frame-based temporal encoding, and pure event-based temporal encoding. The first treats spikes statistically, representing each input sample, typically a pixel, as a spike count within a window of multiple time steps, such as in rate coding paradigms [2], [3], [4], [5], [6]. The second strategy is also frame-based but it encodes input values as spike positions, as in Time to First Spike (TTFS) technique [7], [8], [9]. In contrast, event-based temporal encoding techniques create a time step for each input sampling period and generate spikes when specific events in the input stream occur, such as temporal contrast encoding [10], [11], delta modulation [12], or threshold-based event detection [1]. Most of the FPGA-related works in the literature focus on frame-based encoding. This simplifies event-driven processing by generating sparser and more predictable spikes, but inherently introduces processing latency, due to the window length [13], and cannot capture the characteristics of time sequences [14]. Thus, it does not fit well in key tasks within the near-sensor processing domain, such as anomaly detection [15], time series classification/recognition [16], [17], and sequence-to-sequence decoding/mapping [18].

Conversely, event-based temporal encoding approaches encode precisely time-related features but are rarely supported on FPGA. In this scheme, event-driven SNN inference is less convenient [3]. Moreover, since, in general, spiking activity is less sparse and predictable, loose approaches exploiting sparsity at the neuron level or layer level are less efficient, and finer-grain strategies must be implemented in a tiny power budget.

Our work bridges the gap between SNNs for sensor data processing and FPGAs, supporting event-based temporal encoding and a clock-driven scheme where real-time SNN inferences occur on every input sample, producing an output spike set to be decoded for the classification, or regression results at hand. We present SYNtzuLu,¹ a lightweight near-sensor processing environment for real-time sensor data analysis using SNNs, optimized to fit on the cost-effective Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA, specifically designed for

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¹Pron: [sin-tzu-lu], in Sardinian language *mosquito*, *gnat*.

low-power applications. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- we enable time series data analysis on FPGA-based SNN accelerators, bridging the gap between edge sensor processing and state-of-the-art SNN processors on FPGAs.
- we combine the simplicity of clock-driven execution with the possibility of exploiting sparsity. We dedicate part of the reconfigurable logic to implement a step-by-step activity tracking mechanism, reducing the synapse dynamics processing time when spikes are sparse;
- we put together low-end FPGAs and lightweight SNN models to drastically reduce power consumption and comply with the power and energy requirements of deeply embedded processing systems.

We present the tiny architecture designed for `SYNtzulu` and we show that, despite integrating, on the same FPGA, the SNN engine, a RISC-V softcore for flexible platform management, and encoding and decoding of spikes, its energy consumption per synapse is at least 452x lower than the FPGA-based competitors in literature. Moreover, we assess the system on three use-case SNNs, demonstrating that our lightweight approach can reach state-of-the-art accuracy in sensor data analysis tasks.

The article is organized as follows. Section II discusses related work, providing context for our approach. In Section III, we describe the architecture and discuss processing capabilities and limitations. Section IV presents the use cases referenced for the assessment of the system, the SNN topologies, the training strategies, and the complexity of the SNN models. Section V contains the hardware results in terms of resource occupation and power consumption. Section VI comprises an analysis of the contribution to the power efficiency of each architectural feature, together with an application-related and a technology-related comparison with the state of the art. Finally, Section VII is left for conclusions.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The most efficient implementations of pure SNN processors are neuromorphic ASICs such as Truenorth [19], Spinnaker [20], Loihi [21]. Some of these devices are specifically designed for embedded workloads, as seen in [22] and [23], and provide impressive energy efficiency. Some implementations try to emulate the use of neuromorphic hardware with software-based libraries [24], [25], [26].

Other works in the literature, more related to ours, focus on FPGAs to increase flexibility and integration [27]. Some target the emulation of biorealistic neural tissue, as in [28], and others mostly focus on the execution of SNNs for throughput-oriented processing of event-encoded images and rely on mid- to high-end FPGA devices.

A prominent example is the seminal work in [2], which introduces an event-driven and topology-agnostic SNN accelerator deployed on a Spartan-6 FPGA. The system distributes the workload among 32 cores, each equipped with all the modules necessary to execute its share of neurons. Although the system's validation focuses on the MNIST dataset using a four-layer fully connected network, its architecture can

theoretically accommodate any interconnection among a maximum of 65k neurons and 19 million synapses, using spike packet routing and event queues. In [2], the two most computation-intensive operations involve the identification of post-synaptic neurons and the search for synaptic weights. This highlights a cost associated with highly flexible event-driven systems, which necessitates additional control logic that is not essential for most common-use SNN structures and most near-sensor processing tasks.

In [3], the authors propose an implementation on a Virtex-7 FPGA that integrates 12 processing elements to accelerate the inference of leaky integrate and fire (LIF) neurons in SNNs, featuring online learning. These elements are interconnected through an optimized network-on-chip called Compressed Spike Routing Technique (CSRT). The SNN processor in [3] can switch between event-driven and clock-driven computing paradigms. As reported in the article, the event-driven approach ceases to be beneficial when the time interval between spikes exciting the same neuron is shorter than a predefined threshold. Despite the flexibility to switch between computing schemes, hosting both event-driven and clock-driven circuitry necessitates additional circuitry. This culminates in a method that poses severe requirements in terms of hardware resources, presenting a stark contrast to the less resource-demanding solution suggested in our paper. Moreover, in [3] encoding schemes are not discussed, however, the approach is only demonstrated on rate-encoded data, thus does not fit our initial purpose of serving dynamically varying sensor-data processing.

In [4], authors target a smaller Zynq-7020 device, and focus on the implementation of spiking convolution layers of Integrate and Fire (IF) neurons, mainly on bidimensional input, e.g. images provided by DVS cameras, and rate encoded MNIST images. An optimized module is introduced to execute convolution and pooling simultaneously, with the aim of reducing latency and resource utilization. In addition, [4] presents a high-performance method for executing interconnected dense layers, similar to our approach based on synaptic sparsity. However, the interconnection between convolutional/pooling networks and dense layers appears resource-hungry. Several BRAMs are utilized to perform high-bandwidth access to synaptic weights, followed by accumulation through multiple adder trees, which completely overlooks spike sparsity. This approach diverges from `SYNtzulu`'s paradigm by favoring a resource-hungry strategy aimed at maximizing throughput over leveraging sparsity for energy efficiency. As a result, it does not align with the lightweight sensor data processing perspective characteristic of our work.

The work in [5] aims at even bigger devices, as power results are presented on the Zynq-UltraScale+ platform, and on bigger spiking convolution networks, such as, e.g. VGG. Their approach consists of compressing the inference of multiple time steps into one, which is only feasible in the case of rate-encoded data. In this scenario, LIF neurons are replaced with IF neurons, since spike timing is irrelevant. Under such an assumption, rate encoding paves the way for a new set of possible optimizations that do not apply to event-based temporal-encoded data.

All these works could not be exploited for the implementation of low-power smart sensors as they involve power/energy/cost budgets that are unaffordable for those design cases. An interesting work that addresses a more lightweight implementation is [6], deployed on an Artix-7 FPGA. However, it still presents an SNN accelerator strictly optimized for an SNN experiment on the MNIST dataset. This method takes advantage of the sparsity at every time interval, bypassing whole layers only when the input spike activity is completely absent; otherwise, the whole processing needs to be performed. This case-specific optimization works optimally with rate-encoded MNIST images, as spikes are present only in 1% of the time steps. No indication of similar results with event-based temporal encoded sensor data is provided.

Our paper extends the described state-of-the-art as SYNtzulu is designed to support near-sensor processing for real-time sensor data with event-based temporal encoding, in an ultra-low-power envelope. Unlike alternatives, we demonstrate our approach on the cost- and power-effective Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA, and we assess it on three use cases involving time sequences of sensor data. Although a detailed comparison with the state of the art is provided in Section VI-C, the main architectural innovation in SYNtzulu can be summarized as follows:

- it enables SNN-based time series data analysis on FPGA by exploiting hardware-based configurable encoding slots to execute event-based temporal encoding algorithms in real time;
- it uses reconfigurable logic to implement the management of spike sparsity at synapse-level in a tiny resource budget, to enable neuromorphic-like computation on FPGAs even in case of event-based temporal encoding;
- it leverages hardware resource minimization and lightweight SNN models to drastically reduce power consumption and satisfy deep edge power and energy constraints;
- it exploits fine-grained power management by a compact RISC-V softcore, to adapt to use-case timing and to convert sparsity in power savings.

III. ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

The primary objective of SYNtzulu is to enable the ubiquitous use of FPGA-based SNNs for near-sensor AI. Therefore, the architecture is designed to facilitate real-time analysis of continuous streams of sensor data while maintaining low power consumption. Consequently, as depicted in Fig. 1, our approach envisions incoming sensor data to be encoded into spike bins of multiple channels, each corresponding to sensor data samples, and execute SNN inference in real time for each bin, to obtain an output spike train that can be directly decoded in the result of the task at hand. To achieve this goal, we adopt the following strategies:

- Event-based temporal encoded data, to better capture the features of dynamically varying sensor data [14];
- Clock-driven computing scheme, to handle SNN workload within a tiny resource budget;
- Sparsity awareness, to enable the execution of active synapses alone, improving energy efficiency.

Moreover, we aim at a very low-power implementation, thus we focus our design choices on hardware resource minimization, to target low-power and low-end FPGA devices. Although prospectively implementable on other reconfigurable chips, the system configuration presented in this work is designed for the Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA.

From these approach assumptions, we derive the system architecture described in Fig. 2, which comprehends:

- a configurable *encoding slot* used to preprocess the sensor data and obtain spike trains;
- an *SNN engine* hosting two sub-processors, that is the main computational core in the architecture, in charge of executing the neural network inference;
- a configurable *decoding slot* translating output spike trains into readable data (e.g. classification outcome);
- a RISC-V softcore to handle input/output data flow, power management, and easily configure architecture hyperparameters;

A detailed description of these components is provided in the following sections.

A. SNN Engine

The engine is designed to execute the inference of feed-forward SNNs composed of dense layers of LIF neurons, whose behavior is described by (1).

$$\begin{aligned}
 i(t) &= \sum ws(t-1); \\
 v(t) &= \alpha v(t-1) + i(t); \\
 s(t) &= v(t) > \theta; \\
 v(t) &= v(t) \cdot (1 - s(t))
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

In (1), $i(t)$ is the synaptic current, w is the synaptic weight, s is the spike, $v(t)$ is the membrane potential, α is the decay factor, and θ is the spike threshold.

In dense layers, most operations required to compute (1), are needed to accumulate synaptic weights (the sum in the $i(t)$ computation), according to spikes in input. Thus, we dedicate SIMD-parallel *synaptic adders* to this operation.

Considering that most of the storage capabilities in the iCE40UP5K are provided by four 16-bit wide single-port RAM (SPRAM) memories, we dedicate these blocks to weight storage. We set the synaptic adder to accumulate 4 8-bit weights per cycle received by a pair of SPRAM blocks, and we use 2 parallel sub-processors, each embedding a SIMD-parallel *synaptic adder*, to share the inference workload. Sub-processors are used in time multiplexing to iterate over the neurons in the topology, processing them sequentially until all layers are completed.

In each sub-processor, neuron dynamics are evaluated by a *LIF integration* unit, that receives in input a synaptic current $i(t)$ computed by a *synaptic adder*, updates $v(t)$ and checks the spike condition.

Finally, layer-to-layer connectivity is allowed by the *configurable interconnect*, which routes the spike traffic produced by the *LIF integration* modules, and the *encoding* and *decoding slots* to and from the spike memory (*Spike mem*). The *Spike mem* temporarily stores events produced by each neuron

Fig. 1. Methodology overview, from left to right: (a) sensor data is acquired; (b) every incoming sample is encoded into spikes, (c) across multiple spike channels, according to the event-based temporal encoding algorithm at hand; (d) encoded spikes are timely elaborated by the SNN; (e) each inference encoded output is decoded (f), i.e. interpreted as the result of a regression or a classification.

Fig. 2. Architecture overview: SYNTzulu is composed of a configurable encoding slot, utilized for sample-to-spike conversion, an SNN processor, composed of two sub-processors, which executes SNN inferences, a configurable decoding slot, useful for implementing voting policies during classification tasks, and a RISC-V softcore that handles housekeeping tasks and power management.

for future processing and is composed of two block RAMs (BRAMs) buffers, which the *SNN engine* utilizes alternatively to read and write partial results.

Fig. 3 shows the processing steps performed by SYNTzulu. First, the sensor data is read through an SPI interface, then the *SNN-engine* can proceed to execute the inference layer by layer, evenly dividing the computational load of the layer, the neurons, among the two sub-processors, as shown by the zoom in the figure. Finally, the inference result is decoded and transmitted through a UART interface (not shown). As visible in the zoomed-in detail of Fig. 3, the neuron integration overlaps the computation of synaptic current of the next neuron in the same layer. The execution repeats itself at every sample time; moreover, depending on the workload, the five execution phases, i.e. SPI data transmission, encoding, inference, decoding, and UART data transmission, can be overlapped.

SYNTzulu provides the possibility to introduce arbitrary connection latency between the LIF and the *spike mems*, to support per-neuron axonal delay, which enables an additional degree of freedom in SNN training. This feature has proven pivotal in attaining SoA-aligned classification results in the use case considered in this work.

Fig. 3. Data life-cycle: incoming samples are acquired through an SPI interface (TX1), converted into spikes by the *encoding slot* (E1), processed by the *SNN processor*, which executes the trained model layer by layer (from L1 to L4), elaborated by the *decoding slot* (D1), and streamed out through a UART interface (not shown). The zoom at the bottom of the figure points out that each layer execution is evenly shared by the *Sub-Processors* (Sub-Ps), each iterating over half of the neurons in a layer.

Moreover, event-sparsity exploitation, required to take profit from the SNNs paradigm, is implemented by a key novel

Fig. 4. Sparsity exploitation using spike stack versus available sparsity.

feature: an active spike *stack* module dynamically schedules the loading of synaptic weights to the *synaptic adder*, selecting for processing only active sets of synapses. Thus, it saves operations and extends the stand-by period according to spike sparsity.

1) *Event Sparsity Exploitation*: A main capability of an SNN processing engine, as implemented by most neuromorphic processors, is the possibility of exploiting event sparsity, likely executing the required computation only when triggered by spike events. As mentioned, we use a clock-driven approach, and we add additional synchronous control circuitry that monitors events to save time during the computation of synaptic currents. However, the control logic overhead must be kept limited, selecting an adequate architectural trade-off. To this end, we have chosen to gather synaptic weights into groups and utilize a *spike stack* to skip the computation for all groups not triggered by upstream spikes. Through a design space exploration, we identified groups composed of 4 weights to be an optimal architectural choice in our implementation.

The stack unit tracks, neuron by neuron, which weight groups need to be loaded from the weight memory and the corresponding addresses. Groups including weights that are not triggered by upstream events (i.e. corresponding to 4 non-firing neurons) are not noted in the stack, thus the corresponding computation is avoided and sparsity is exploited.

The dashed line in Fig. 4 shows an example measure of sparsity, i.e. the percentage of inactive synapses, over a recording of twenty seconds from a dataset related to one of our use cases. The solid line illustrates the actual sparsity that is exploitable by considering the grouping of four employed by the *spike stack*.

A single active weight is sufficient to activate a whole group; therefore, larger groups exploit sparsity less efficiently. On the other hand, smaller groups require larger stacks, increasing control overhead. In Table I, we report part of the analysis performed to select 4 as the optimal group size for the current deployment. Considering a layer with 128 inputs, a configuration with one-weight or two-weight groups would better exploit spike sparsity than our four-weight group setup, however, both alternatives would occupy too many logic cells (LCs), up to 34% of the total available. In contrast, the configuration with 8 weights per group is not as efficient as the one with four weights in exploiting spike sparsity.

2) *Axonal Delay Implementation*: The axonal delay is the physiological latency associated with the transmission of spikes along axons from presynaptic to postsynaptic neurons. From an algorithmic perspective, miming the axonal delay

TABLE I
STACK SIZE EXPLORATION ON LATTICE ICE40UP5K

Set size	Stack size [LC]	Sparsity	Utilization
1	896	95%	34.0%
2	384	90%	14.6%
4	160	81%	6.1%
8	64	66%	2.4%

helps training to increase the SNN memory, improving results, especially in time-sensitive tasks such as sensor data analysis. The axonal delay unit hosted in SYNtZulu allows customization of the axonal delay per neuron, from 0 to 63 time steps. The module architecture consists of two BRAMs. The first BRAM stores the delay corresponding to each neuron in terms of time steps, as identified offline during training. The second is used as a FIFO, i.e. stores an array of 63 binary slots corresponding to a history of the spiking activity in the last 63 time steps. The two BRAMs are accessed concurrently. For each neuron under consideration, the corresponding axonal delay loaded from the delay BRAM is used to compose the address for the FIFO BRAM, to identify which location of the FIFO should be propagated as output.

B. Encoding/Decoding Slots

SYNtZulu's *SNN engine* is wrapped by configurable encoding and decoding slots. Such slots can be used to map application-specific logic to adapt to different use cases, interfacing the *SNN processor* with the continuous sensor data flow at hand, on the input side, and with the target algorithm result evaluation method, on the output side.

The *encoding slot* can be customized to implement a wide range of methods to convert input data into spike trains. As will be shown in the following, FPGA resources that are left unused by the *SNN engine* are sufficient to implement fairly complex DSP-intensive methods, including data preprocessing on significant numbers of channels and acquisition rates. The *decoding slot* interprets the output spike trains generated by the *SNN engine* providing usable output, such as the result of a regression or the outcome of a classification task.

The *encoding slot* includes three cascade-connected modules:

- A BRAM-based input buffer is used to store the raw input samples received through the SPI interface;
- An application-specific module executes the encoding algorithm on the samples stored in the input buffer, generating spikes serially;
- A serial-to-parallel converter adapts the serial spike bus to the four-lane spike bus of the SNN engine.

The input buffer serves the purpose of gating the rest of the *encoding slot* during low-rate data transmission. However, it is optional and can be removed if BRAM resources are in short supply. More details on the application-specific module of the *encoding slot* are given in Section IV-A.

The *decoding slot* is inherently simpler than the *encoding slot*, and in some cases it may not be required at all. For

TABLE II
USE CASE DESCRIPTION SUMMARY

	iEEG	ECG	sEMG
Task	Neural signal decoder	Arrhythmia classification	Gesture classification
Input type	iEEG from the motor cortex sampled by a Utah microelectrode array	ECG single-lead signal recorded using a modified limb	sEMG signal from the forearm sampled by two Thalmic Myo armbands
Output type	4 finger forces, 1 velocity	5-class classification task	13-class classification task
Encoding	Spike detection	Peak detection and heart-beat delta encoding	Delta encoding
Decoding	None	Spike rate ranking	Spike rate ranking
Channels @ Fs	96 @ 10 kHz	1 @ 360 Hz	16 @ 200 Hz
Real-time constraints	One inference per millisecond	bpm-dependent, classifications on 292-sample windows	One classification every 0.1 s on 200-sample windows

example, in regression tasks, the decoding slot is unnecessary, as the neuron potential in the last layer of the network serves directly as the output. However, in classification tasks, spike-rate ranking is essential. This involves counting the spikes fired by the neurons in the last layer within a time window and determining the winner through a comparator tree.

C. RISC-V Controller and Middleware

The system embeds a SERIAL RISC-V (SERV) core,² which features an extremely resource-efficient bit-serial design. SERV does not participate in executing SNN or signal processing workloads, as its limited performance of a single operation every 32 clock cycles would not be of help. However, it allows for easily reconfiguring the system from experiment to experiment by reprogramming its firmware, which can be compiled using the RISC-V cross-compiler, and enable control over several memory-mapped peripherals through load/store operations, such as:

- a) SPI and UART data transfer:
 - Synaptic weights loading from SPI flash drive;
 - Input sample stream through SPI (21 Mbps);
 - Output inference transfer through UART (115,200 bps);
- b) Power management;
- c) *Encoding* and *decoding slots* parameters.

The middleware, after an initialization phase, utilizes an interrupt mechanism driven by a timer to cyclically require new streams of samples.

D. Processing Capabilities and Limitations

SYNTzulu, as said, supports the execution of SNNs composed of dense layers of LIF neurons using fixed-point arithmetic, as detailed in Table III. The inference time of a specific SNN in SYNTzulu is directly determined by the sparsity of the data, the number of synapses, and the

TABLE III

LIF NEURON FIXED-POINT REPRESENTATION								
Term	w	I	v	s	α	θ	Axonal Delay	Delay FIFO
Dimension [bit]	8	15	16	1	16	16	6	63

time required for the computation of the synaptic current. All the other operations occur in parallel, and their execution is overlapped. Thus, we can use (2) to evaluate the inference execution time T_{inf} in clock cycles.

$$T_{inf} = \frac{(1 - \text{sparsity}) \times \text{number of synapses}}{\text{number of sub-processors} \times \text{SIMD ways}} \quad (2)$$

The number of sub-processors and SIMD ways are set to 2 and 4 in the current version, as we deployed 8-bit quantized models, corresponding to a maximum weight memory bandwidth of eight weights per clock cycle. The clock frequency considered in this paper is 22 MHz. Throughput should be compliant with the constraints posed by the target use case in terms of sample rate and inference rates. On the other hand, the main memory limitation to the usage of SYNTzulu is the weight memory size, which poses a limit to the number of synapses in the SNN under execution. The memory can be built with different compositions of on-FPGA storage macro, however, the presented system is capable of storing 131,072 8-bit weights.

IV. USE CASES AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this section, we present three use cases to assess SYNTzulu's performance in relevant scenarios. These use cases, summarized in Table II, represent typical examples of real-time and power-constrained applications, exhibiting varying levels of complexity in terms of inference rate and data bandwidth. We also outline the SNN network topologies, the training strategy, and the complexity of the models.

²<https://github.com/olofk/serv>

A. Use Case Description

1) *Use Case 1 - iEEG Neural Decoding*: SYNtZulu was validated on a continuous decoding problem, where a macaque monkey performs a delayed reach-to-grasp task [29]. The task involves the decoding of the intracortical neural signal of the motor cortex sampled at 30 kHz (downsampled at 10 kHz in this study) using a 96-channel microelectrode array (MEA), to infer five output signals, i.e. the velocity of the moved object and the strength applied by the subject fingers, at 1 kHz sampling frequency.

The *encoding slot* is configured to feed the SNN according to the timing of intracortical biological spikes, i.e. typical bursts of electrical activity produced by neurons. This process involves low-pass filtering, spike waveform emphasizing, noise-based adaptive threshold evaluation, and threshold crossing detection. Finally, spike binning adapts the spike rate to 1 kHz to match the desired output sampling rate.

The *decoding slot* is not used in the iEEG use case, since the output variables of the inference are directly computed as the potential of the neurons in the last layer.

Details about the implementation can be found in [30].

2) *Use Case 2 - ECG Arrhythmia Classification*: SYNtZulu was tested on a detection and classification problem. The system is designed to detect arrhythmias from a single-lead ECG signal [31] sampled at 360 Hz, classifying beats into 5 classes.

The *encoding slot* is configured to perform two steps: a) peak detection, which identifies signal windows consisting of 300 samples corresponding to heartbeats, according to a hardware-optimized version of the Pan–Tompkins algorithm; b) delta-modulation, where 6-channel spike trains are generated from the sample windows. The modulator observes the changes in the input signals, as well as their first and second derivatives. It assigns a spike to a positive/negative channel whenever the monitored variable increases/decreases by an offline-selected delta.

The *decoding slot* counts the spikes produced by the SNN output neurons and selects the classification result by identifying the output neuron with the highest spiking rate.

Details about the implementation can be found in [32].

3) *Use Case 3 - sEMG Gesture Classification*: SYNtZulu was tested on the Ninapro DB5-E1 hand gesture classification task [33], where sEMG data from 10 subjects who performed 12 distinct hand movements were collected using two Thalmic Myo armbands, each providing signals from 8 channels, sampled at 200 Hz.

The *encoding slot* is configured to perform delta modulation on the raw sEMG signal and its first and second derivatives, as in the ECG use case, providing the *SNN engine* with six spike trains per input channel, resulting in a total of 96 channels. The *decoding slot* behaves as in the ECG use case.

Details about the implementation can be found in [34].

B. SNNs Topology and Training Strategy

After a Design Space Exploration (DSE) aimed at finding an adequate topology executable by our system configuration,

TABLE IV
SNN MODELS TOPOLOGY, TRAINING, AND COMPLEXITY SUMMARY

		iEEG	ECG	sEMG
Neurons	Input	96	6	96
	Layer 1	64	64	64
	Layer 2	128	128	128
	Layer 3	64	64	64
	Layer 4	5	5	13
Params	Synapses	22,848	17,088	23,360
	Neurons	261	261	269
Training	Loss	MSE	<i>SpikeRate</i>	<i>SpikeRate</i>
	Learning rate	1e-3	1e-3	1e-3 1e-4 1e-5
	Batch	1	32	32
	Axonal delay	no	yes	yes
Complexity	Memory [kB]	22.8	19.5	25.7
	Operations [Mops]	0.023	5.14	4.78
	Throughput [Mops/s]	23.4	5.14	47.8
Power	Accuracy	0.84	98.4%	85.6%
	Inference [mW]	12.05	12.05	12.05
	Average [mW]	9.87	1.45	1.72

we have trained similar SNNs for the three use cases. The SNNs differ in the number of neurons for the first and last layers, which are matched to the input/output characteristics of the task. The resulting topologies are highlighted in Table IV.

For the SNNs training, we have used the PyTorch package SLAYER (Spike LAYER Error Reassignment), embedded into the LAVA software framework [35], executed on a T4 GPU, available in the Google Colab platform.

The iEEG use case is a regression task, where we utilized the Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the neurons' potentials in the last layer of the network and the target variables as a loss function, as reported in Table IV. Therefore, each output neuron potential maps one of the five target variables, and its firing condition is disabled to avoid resetting the potential to zero.

Conversely, ECG and sEMG use cases are classification problems. Therefore, we employed a different strategy. In this case, every output neuron maps a different class, thus, in the ECG use case the model presents five output neurons, whereas thirteen neurons constitute the output layer in the sEMG use case. The models are trained using the *SpikeRate* loss function of SLAYER, which trains the output neurons to fire spikes at a certain rate when the mapped class is recognized. We set the true rate at 0.2 and the false rate at 0.03. Moreover, in classification tasks, we found that enabling axonal delay training was fundamental to obtaining state-of-the-art accuracy. Axonal delay tuning allows to define a different propagation time of the spikes to the post-synaptic neurons. This feature has been exploited for layers 1, 2, and 3, selecting a maximum delay of 63 time steps.

After training, the models were mapped to a fixed-point representation, as detailed in Table III, without compromising accuracy. This process employed observers to obtain scaling values and monitor the dynamics of potentials.

TABLE V
RESOURCE USAGE ON LATTICE ICE40UP5K

Module	LC	DSP	BRAM	SPRAM
iEEG	4,528 (85%)	2 (25%)	24 (80%)	4 (100%)
ECG	4,690 (89%)	3 (38%)	28 (93%)	4 (100%)
sEMG	4,243 (80%)	2 (25%)	25 (83%)	4 (100%)

C. Model Complexity

The overall memory required by the models is reported in Table IV and can be derived using Table III.

The complexity of the models in terms of operations per inference/classification and the required throughput to satisfy the corresponding real-time constraints are also reported in Table IV (for details about the inference/classification rate please refer to Table II). The complexity of the three use cases differs significantly, even though the models are of similar size. Indeed, a different number of inferences per second is necessary, depending on the requirements.

We preliminary report in Table IV also the numbers of power consumption that will be explained later in Section V-B. We show both the peak power measured during inference when the models are deployed on `SYNtZulu` and the average power during the entire sampling cycle, as the SNN execution time often falls short compared to the sample time. Thus, we discuss average power, measured as the energy dissipated over the whole sampling period. The models' executions present the same power consumption during inference, however, depending on workload and data transfer, the average power varies significantly. We set the system to run at maximum clock frequency during inference, to comply with worst-case scenarios, and we consider the possibility of power saving when there is idle time between two successive input samples. Finally, Table IV reports the accuracy obtained in the three use cases, which are aligned to the state of the art, and will be discussed in Section VI-B.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we detail the performance of the system on the three use cases in terms of FPGA resource utilization and power consumption to assess the quality of the overall integration.

A. Resource Occupation

Logic synthesis and implementation were carried out using an architecture-neutral FPGA framework including Yosys Open SYnthesis Suite (Yosys) for logic synthesis, and Netxtnpr for placement, routing, and bitstream generation [36]. The Lattice iCE40UP5K hosts 5,280 LCs embedding both a 4-bit input LUT and a flip-flop (FF), 30 4-kb BRAM tiles, 4 256-kb SPRAMs, and 8 DSP slices containing 16×16 -bit multipliers.

Resource utilization is shown in Table V.

LC utilization reached 89% in the worst-case scenario of the ECG use case, indicating the potential for accommodating even more demanding encoding algorithms. All embedded SPRAMs are utilized, although not fully, suggesting that larger

TABLE VI
OPERATING MODES POWER CONSUMPTION

	$P_{V_{CORE}}$	$P_{V_{CCIO0\&1}}$	$P_{V_{CCIO2}}$	P_{tot}
<i>Stand-by</i>	0.35 mW	0.94 mW	0	1.29 mW
<i>Data-transfer</i>	9.67 mW	3.8 mW	0	13.47 mW
<i>Inference</i>	11.11 mW	0.94 mW	0	12.05 mW

SNNs can be executed. The BRAM utilization ranges between 80% and 93%, with BRAM resources distributed across the system to conserve LCs. Finally, 2 DSPs are employed to integrate the neurons in the *SNN engine*, and one DSP is used in the *ECG encoding slot*.

B. Power/Energy Consumption

The embedded RISC-V softcore allows to selectively gate the main modules of the architecture, such as the *SNN engine*, the I/O interface, the *encoding*, and *decoding slot*, and the softcore itself. Thus, three different operating modes are possible:

- Stand-by mode: the system is fully gated, except for the logic responsible for periodically awakening the system to read new input data streams, clocked at 10 kHz;
- Data-transfer mode: the system encodes data samples incoming on the SPI interface via the *encoding slot*;
- Inference: the SNN processor executes inferences on encoded data.

Note that the softcore is only temporarily active when it is needed to switch from one operating mode to another. For example, in our worst-case scenario of the iEEG use case the softcore is active for the 45.6% of the sample time.

The power consumption of each operating mode, measured in our worst-case scenario of the iEEG use case, is available in Table VI, and was obtained by clocking the system at 22 MHz and measuring the voltage drop across three shunt resistors having a nominal value of $3.3 \pm 0.033 \Omega$. These resistors were connected between the three power supplies of the Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA prototype board, i.e. ICEBreaker V1.0e, known as V_{CORE} , $V_{CCIO0\&1}$, and V_{CCIO2} . V_{CORE} supplies 1.2 V to the internal FPGA components, and $V_{CCIO0\&1}$ and V_{CCIO2} provide the I/O pins with 3.3 V.

The system's time allocation across the three operating modes varies depending on the application workload. The time spent in *Data-transfer* operating mode depends on factors such as sampling rate and data packet size. The time spent in *Inference* operating mode depends on the inference rate and the inference execution time. Table IV shows the average power consumption for the three use cases.

Remarkably, enabling the stack unit - the architectural solution employed to enable `SYNtZulu` to exploit spike sparsity - and optimizing the stand-by power, resulted in reduced average power consumption and possibly longer battery life compared to the power consumption during inference. A detailed analysis of the contribution of each architectural feature in terms of energy efficiency is available in Section VI-A.

VI. DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss the architectural optimization results in terms of average power efficiency. Moreover,

TABLE VII

APPLICATION-RELATED COMPARISON WITH THE SOA

Use case	Dataset	Reference	Platform	Device	Sampling frequency	RT constraint	Inference time	Accuracy	Inference power	Energy
iEEG	[29]	[30]	FPGA	Artix-7	10 kHz	1 ms	14 μ s	0.84	56.4 mW	789.60 nJ
iEEG	[29]	our	FPGA	iCE40UP5K	10 kHz	1 ms	25 μ s	0.84	12.05 mW	301.25 nJ
ECG	[37]	[38]	FPGA	Zynq-7000	N/A	N/A	N/A	85%	176 mW	N/A
ECG	[31]	[39]	FPGA	N/A	360 Hz	bpm-dependent	1.32 ms	98.26%	250 mW	324.51 μ J
ECG	[31]	our	FPGA	iCE40UP5K	360 Hz	bpm-dependent	6.5 ms	98.4%	12.05 mW	78.33 μ J
sEMG	Custom	[40]	ASIC	SpiNNaker	250 Hz	400 ms	N/A	84.8%	1–4 W	N/A
sEMG	[33]	[41]	ASIC	Loihi	1000 Hz	300 ms	5.7 ms	74%	41 mW	246 mJ
sEMG	[33]	our	FPGA	iCE40UP5K	200 Hz	100 ms	3.94 ms	85.6%	12.05 mW	47.48 μ J

Fig. 5. Architecture choices and power efficiency gains per use case.

we compare the achieved accuracy and power figure with state-of-the-art SNNs deployed on various embedded computing platforms. Finally, we present an application-agnostic comparative analysis with other FPGA-based SNN accelerators from the literature.

A. Power Efficiency Contributions of Architectural Features

We present an analysis of the gains achieved through various architectural features implemented in SYNtZulu. We investigate the impact of each feature and provide an overview of their contributions.

Fig. 5 illustrates the impact of each architectural feature on average power in various use cases. A main important choice has been our focus on resource minimization (model quantization, SERV softcore, optimized stack architecture). By keeping resource requirements to a minimum, we were capable of fitting in the low-power Lattice iCE40UP5K FPGA. Considering such a low-end target provides significant advantages with respect to other alternatives. For example, it provides a substantial 4.45x improvement in power efficiency on average in the three use cases with respect to a baseline implementation on a mid-size Xilinx Artix-7 XC7A100T FPGA (same as used in [30]). Such a device, being bigger and optimized for higher maximum performance, is less efficient on our power envelope. As a note, it dissipates 82 mW only as quiescent power.³

³The value was estimated using Xilinx Power Estimator.

Moreover, incorporating support for selectively gating the main system modules effectively minimizes power consumption during inference, data transmission, and idle states, resulting in average power savings ranging from 1.31x to 6.14x, depending on the application workload. Noteworthy, with power management handled by the softcore, the resource overhead for clock gating remains minimal, comprising only 25 LCs.

Finally, integrating support for sparsity awareness via the spike stack allows for the omission of redundant computations, leading to average power savings ranging from 1.12x to 1.64x, at a marginal cost of 7% of SYNtZulu’s LCs.

B. Application-Related Comparison With the SoA

In Table VII we report accuracy values achieved by other SNN approaches on the same dataset as long as the respective power consumption. In the iEEG use case, the accuracy is a cross-correlation metric, in the ECG and sEMG use cases, the metric is the classification accuracy. In all the use cases, the SNNs executed on SYNtZulu not only align with existing literature alternatives or surpass them in terms of accuracy but also exhibit reduced power consumption. This underscores the applicability of our architecture to the considered class of applications.

For example, in the iEEG use case, SYNtZulu achieves the same accuracy as in [30], while absorbing 4.68 times less power and being 2.62 times more energy efficient during inference. As indicated by the analysis in Section VI-A, the most important contribution in the iEEG use case is due to the target FPGA (3.87x in our tests). In this use case, clock gating is only used on the SNN as the IO circuitry is constantly active, thus, the other saving strategies are more marginally exploited.

In the ECG use case, the work in [38] proposes a binarized SNN deployed on an FPGA of the Zynq-7000 family. While its classification performance cannot be directly compared to ours, as it was evaluated on a slightly different task (distinguishing abnormal from normal beats on the PTB Diagnostic ECG Database [37]), it provides an additional reference for the power consumption of FPGA-based implementations. The study reports an average power consumption of 176 mW, which is 14.61 times higher than in this work. Another relevant reference is the work by [39], which presents a portable ECG monitoring system based on FPGA. It achieves classification accuracy comparable to ours on the same dataset

TABLE VIII
TECHNOLOGY-RELATED COMPARISON WITH THE SOA

Work	Data	FPGA	Clock/Event	Sparsity	Encoding	Inference power	mW/MHz	Energy/synapse
our	Sensors	iCE40UP5K	Clock-driven	Synapse	Event-based temporal encoding	12.05 mW	0.54	0.062 nJ
[2]	MNIST	Spartan-6	Event-driven	Neuron/Synapse	Frame-based rate encoding	1.5 W	20	-
[3]	MNIST	Virtex-7	Both	Neuron/Synapse	Frame-based rate encoding	1.6 W	16	28 nJ
[4]	MNIST	XA7Z020	Clock-driven	Synapse*	Frame-based rate encoding	280 mW	2.8	-
[5]	MNIST	ZCU102	Event-driven	Neuron/Synapse	Frame-based rate encoding	400 mW	2	-
[6]	MNIST	Artix-7	Clock-driven	Layer	Frame-based rate encoding	-	-	41 nJ

Only partially exploited*

but requires 20.75 times higher peak power during inference and is 4.14 times less energy efficient. In the ECG scenario, optimizing the design to operate within a constrained resource environment while meeting the real-time constraints dictated by the task at hand has consistently proven to be the most energy-efficient approach.

In the sEMG use case, the study by [40] utilizes SpiNNaker to address a similar problem on a different dataset involving only four movements, with more relaxed real-time constraints of 400 ms. While a direct accuracy comparison is not immediately feasible, their results demonstrate classification accuracy similar to ours, albeit with power consumption ranging between 83 and 332 times higher than in our work. Additionally, [41] presents an SNN deployed on the Loihi neuromorphic chip, trained on the same dataset used in our study. Their system exhibits lower classification accuracy, along with longer inference times and higher energy consumption per classification. These findings underscore that our approach is particularly well-suited for tasks that can be addressed using lightweight SNNs, even when the comparison involves mainstream neuromorphic processors.

C. Technology-Related Comparison With the SoA

To complete the assessment, Table VIII presents a comparative analysis with other FPGA-based SNN accelerators documented in the literature. Notably, these alternatives do not prioritize real-time analysis of sensor data. Instead, they are optimized for achieving high throughput within the classification of rate-encoded MNIST samples, employing larger FPGAs, leading to significantly higher power consumption.

In contrast, the presented architecture is tailored to target a smaller reconfigurable device. As a result, we managed to cap the peak power dissipation at 12.05 mW during inference. This differs significantly from alternatives, such as the approach described in [4], which, despite having the lowest peak power during inference among the other MNIST classifiers, exhibits power consumption 23 times higher than our work, being much more resource-hungry and thus being hosted on a mid-end XA7Z020 FPGA.

When it comes to frequency-normalized power, SYNtzulu dissipates only 0.54 mW per MHz during inference, at least 3.7 times lower than the best case among the related works [5], where an event-driven computing scheme is emulated on a high-end ZCU102 FPGA.

In terms of workload-normalized metrics, SYNtzulu dissipates only 62 pJ per synapse, around 452 times less than [3], where a Virtex-7 FPGA hosts a design capable of switching

between clock-driven and event-driven computing schemes, and about 661 times less than [6], where a less complex architecture deployed on an Artix-7 FPGA only exploits sparsity at the layer level, i.e. avoiding computations only when all the inputs are inactive.

The technology-related comparison shows how SYNtzulu represents a near-optimal computing platform whenever the SNN size required by the task at hand complies with its storage resources. Moreover, the comparison in Table VIII does not account for dynamic power management. As detailed in Section V-B, figures could be further improved by employing fine-grained power control to create operating modes that reduce consumption by up to nine times with respect to the peak reported in the table. When used in conjunction with sparsity awareness, energy consumption can be reduced from 32% to 88%, while utilizing only 320 LCs.

VII. CONCLUSION

We introduced SYNtzulu, an SNN inference platform tailored to be implemented on low-end and low-power FPGAs. SYNtzulu enhances flexibility and reusability by integrating a RISC-V softcore, a configurable interconnect, and two customizable encoding and decoding slots.

To the best of our knowledge, SYNtzulu is the first work that exploits a clock-driven processing scheme for SNNs on a low-end FPGA while focusing on event-based temporal encoding, closing the gap between deep-edge sensor data processing and SNN executions on FPGAs.

Evaluated power/energy metrics underscore that, when the nature of the task (and subsequently the SNN algorithm) allows for a lightweight approach, SYNtzulu can be leveraged to create notably efficient near-sensor processing nodes.

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